

Inhibitory effects of insecticides on entomogenous fungi *Metarrhizium anisopliae* and *Beauveria bassiana*

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M. anisopliae and *B. bassiana* are the most commonly isolated entomogenous fungi from field-collected brown planthopper (BPH) in the Philippines. Because BPH resurgence is linked with insecticide application, it may be that insecticide applied to control BPH also inhibit natural enemies of BPH. We evaluated the effect of insecticides recommended for BPH control and BPH resurgence-causing insecticides on the germination of *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* spores. Insecticide was mixed into the culture media before planting, or was surface-applied on hardened media. All insecticides significantly reduced spore germination of both fungi (see table). *M. anisopliae* was more sensitive to insecticides. Recommended insecticides reduced spore germination more than resurgence-causing insecticides did, probably because a higher dosage of the recommended insecticide was applied.

Because both types of insecticides greatly inhibited spore germination of both fungi, it is unlikely that insecticides cause resurgence by counteracting the beneficial effect of entomogenous fungi. Among the BPH resurgence-causing insecticides, deltamethrin, the most powerful, had the weakest effect on spore germination. Only methyl parathion, the second most powerful BPH resurgence-causing insecticide, greatly reduced spore germination.

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Effect of insecticides on *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* spore germination, IRRI, 1983.

Insecticide	Spore germination ^a (%)			
	Insecticide mixed with media ^b		Insecticide on media surface ^c	
	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>
		<i>Recommended for BPH control^d</i>		
Monocrotophos	0 c	32 b	72 b	95 b
BPMC	1 b	2 c	36 d	36 d
Carbosulfan	0 c	0 d	66 c	68 c
Azinphos ethyl + BPMC	0 c	0 d	28 e	68 c
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	0	9	51	67
		<i>Causing BPH resurgence^e</i>		
Azinphos ethyl	20 d	71 c	16 d	77 c
Deltamethrin	56 c	90 b	81 b	89 b
Methyl parathion	0 e	6 e	15 d	72 d
MIPC	66 b	38 d	75 c	67 e
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	36	51	47	77

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. 300 random spores counted 24 h after insecticide application. ^bInsecticide mixed with the culture media at 40-45°C, then plated. Fungal spore suspension (0.3 ml/petri dish) was spread on the cooled and hardened media. ^cInsecticides and fungi spores were mixed together in suspension and 0.3 ml/petri dish was spread on top of the hardened culture media. ^dAt the national recommended rate of 0.75 kg ai/ha. ^eAt the minimal rate that causes resurgence (0.50 kg ai/ha, except deltamethrin at 0.025 kg ai/ha).